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Addressing Coastal Plastic Waste through the DPSIR Approach: Case Studies from Tasikmalaya and Sancang, Garut, Indonesia

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Abstract

The Driving Forces, State, Impact, and Response (DPSIR) framework is used in this study to look at the growing problem of macroplastic waste on the coast of Tasikmalaya and Sancang, Garut, in West Java, Indonesia. These coastal areas, known for their natural beauty and tourist appeal, face significant environmental threats due to the accumulation of plastic waste. The research identifies human activities, particularly the increase in tourism and settlement, as the primary drivers contributing to waste accumulation, posing risks to marine ecosystems, public health, and the socio-economic fabric of the region. The coastal environment has deteriorated as a result of these pressures, which is evident in the presence of difficult-to-degrade macroplastic waste. The impact of this pollution is profound, affecting biodiversity, ecosystem health, and the aesthetic and recreational value of the beaches. In response, the study suggests a multifaceted approach involving improved waste management practices, environmental education, and the establishment of adequate waste disposal facilities. It emphasizes the need for collaborative efforts among government, local communities, and tourism managers to restore ecosystems and ensure the sustainability of tourism in the area. Through a comprehensive review of literature and field observations conducted in May 2023, this research highlights the critical role of the DPSIR framework in understanding and addressing environmental challenges in coastal regions, advocating for integrated environmental management and policy-making.

Keywords : DPSIR, Tasikmalaya, Garut, Coastal

Introduction

The coastal tourism areas of West Java boast numerous advantages, notably in the southern coastal regions that border the Indian Ocean. These southern coasts, including Tasikmalaya and Sancang in Garut, offer natural landscapes that attract tourists (Ningsih et al., 2020; Winoto et al., 2022). These areas have evolved into residential and tourist zones, influenced by coastal activities and human interaction (Kasman & Triokmen, 2021; Ningsih et al., 2020; Suprpto et al., 2016). Anthropogenic activities in these coastal areas

can lead to issues such as waste accumulation, posing threats to marine ecosystems, human health, navigation safety, beach aesthetics, and socio-economic aspects (Ningsih et al., 2020; Poluan et al., 2023). Implementing the DPSIR (Drivers, Pressures, State, Impact, Response) method offers a strategic approach to tackle waste issues in Tasikmalaya and Leuweung Sancang, Garut. Initially, 'Drivers' are identified as the growth in tourism and settlement activities in coastal areas, leading to 'Pressures' from increased waste production by tourists and locals. The 'State' reveals waste accumulation on beaches, threatening biodiversity and natural beauty. The 'Impact' includes coastal ecosystem degradation, marine habitat damage, and diminished tourism experiences. In 'Response', efforts such as improved waste management, adequate waste disposal facilities at tourist sites, environmental cleanliness education for communities and tourists, and recycling systems are necessary. Cooperation among government, local communities, and tourism managers for conservation and ecosystem restoration programs is essential. Through the DPSIR approach, these comprehensive efforts aim to reduce environmental pressure, restore ecosystems, and mitigate negative impacts on biodiversity and tourism sustainability in the area. Further environmental management and analysis can be conducted using the DPSIR method, connecting social, political, economic, and environmental conditions (Quevedo et al., 2022). This method assesses environmental impacts based on surveys and observations, analyzes 'Drivers' or causes of environmental changes, which are human activities causing 'Pressures' on the environment (Hendriarianti et al., 2022; Zulkifli, 2013). From analyzing these causes, pressures, states, and impacts, the role or response of the government and local communities is sought (Batubara, 2014). The DPSIR framework is valuable for environmental management, widely applied by researchers, and effective in identifying causes of environmental damage and linking them to institutional and policy responses (Dzoga et al., 2020).

The escalating issue of macroplastic waste at four beaches deemed dirty within the Tasikmalaya and Sancang, Garut regions underscores a pressing environmental crisis, necessitating a comprehensive analysis and strategic response. Utilizing the DPSIR (Drivers, Pressures, State, Impact, Response) framework, this analysis aims to dissect the multifaceted contributors to plastic pollution, spotlighting the urgent need for enhanced waste management practices in these coastal vicinities. The drivers, including booming tourism, a glaring lack of environmental cleanliness awareness, an uptick in visitor numbers, insufficient waste disposal infrastructures, and the omnipresence of fishing activities, collectively exacerbate the pressures on these ecosystems. These pressures manifest as an augmented presence of hard-to-degrade macroplastic waste, subsequently deteriorating the state of the beaches into categories marked as polluted. The resultant impacts are far-reaching, threatening biodiversity, damaging pristine ecosystems, and diminishing the beaches' aesthetic and recreational appeal. Despite the initiation of response measures around the Tasikmalaya District, the effectiveness of these efforts remains suboptimal and incompletely implemented. This analysis not only illuminates the current inadequacies in addressing the macroplastic waste dilemma but also serves as a clarion call to coastal communities and stakeholders in Tasikmalaya and Sancang, Garut. It advocates for a concerted and holistic approach to waste management, aiming to mitigate the adverse environmental impacts and restore the natural beauty and ecological balance of the affected beaches.

Methodology

In the methodology of this research, the DPSIR (Drivers, Pressures, State, Impact, Response) framework is meticulously employed to analyze the complexities surrounding waste accumulation on coastal areas, specifically at Pantai Karantawulan, Pantai Cipatujah, Pantai Sindangkerta, Pantai Pamayangsari, Pantai Bubujung, Pantai Cikolomberan Sancang, and Pantai Cetut. Drawing upon a comprehensive review of literature as the primary data source, this approach systematically dissects the environmental challenges through a multi-dimensional lens. Human activities, identified as 'Drivers', are scrutinized for their role in exerting 'Pressures' on the environment, a concept well-documented by Hendriarianti et al. (2022) and Zulkifli (2013). These activities, ranging from basic needs like housing and food, underscore the intimate relationship between human necessities and environmental stress (Zulkifli, 2013).

The 'Pressures' resulting from these drivers, as posited by Zulkifli (2013), significantly alter the 'State' of the environment, leading to tangible changes in the physical condition of these coastal regions. This alteration, in turn, triggers a series of 'Impacts' that resonate through the ecosystem, public health, and the socio-economic fabric of the community, aligning with Zulkifli's (2013) insights on the cascading effects of environmental pressures. The 'Response' mechanism, a crucial aspect of the DPSIR framework, encapsulates the collective and individual actions undertaken by communities and stakeholders to address and mitigate the adverse effects of coastal waste, suggesting the implementation of new regulations, management strategies, and other initiatives as potential solutions.

This research methodology, underpinned by the DPSIR framework, not only facilitates a holistic understanding of the environmental predicament faced by these coastal areas but also underscores the importance of a strategic and informed response to counteract the negative impacts of waste accumulation. Through the lens of Hendriarianti et al. (2022) and Zulkifli (2013), the study navigates the intricate interplay between human actions and environmental responses, advocating for an integrated approach to environmental management and policy-making that is both adaptive and proactive in nature.

Results and Discussion

The DPSIR framework was applied in this study to identify various factors or drivers (D), pressures (P), impacts (I), and responses (R) related to the presence of macroplastic waste on seven beaches along the coasts of Tasikmalaya and Sancang, Garut. This qualitative analysis was based on field observations conducted in May 2023, as well as a review of existing literature. The DPSIR analysis focused on four out of the seven beaches categorized as dirty.

Drivers

According to Kristensen (2004), the "drivers" component refers to factors that can change the ecosystem, either directly or indirectly, originating from environmental, economic, and social aspects. This research identified the accumulation of waste on dirty-category beaches as a driver. Beaches like Karangtawulan, Cipatujah, and Sindangkerta, developed for tourism, show a direct correlation between tourist activities and the increase in waste. The influx of tourists, often bringing food and drinks in plastic packaging, contributes significantly to waste accumulation. Despite the challenging access to Karangtawulan Beach, located below a steep cliff, its popularity for camping does not excuse the lack of waste disposal facilities, leading to littering. Unlike Karangtawulan, Cipatujah and Sindangkerta Beaches have easier access, yet the environmental awareness among

visitors is low, and the available waste disposal facilities are insufficient, encouraging littering. The presence of plastic waste, such as polypropylene (PP) at Karangtawulan, low-density polyethylene (LDPE) at Cipatujah, and expandable polystyrene (PS-E) at Sindangkerta, indicates a lack of awareness and the impact of tourism. Additionally, Cipatujah Beach suffers from waste brought in by the Cipatujah River. Pamayangsari Beach, less frequented by tourists and used as a fishing port, experiences waste issues from the fishing community, marked by the presence of PS-E waste and used fishing gear, reflecting a general lack of environmental awareness and adequate waste disposal facilities.

Pressure

Following Abalansa et al. (2020), pressures arise directly from the drivers, where tourism activities and low environmental awareness contribute to the increasing presence of plastic waste. The lack of waste disposal facilities near the beaches adds to this pressure, making the degradation of plastic, which can take hundreds of years, a significant environmental challenge.

State

As Zulkifli (2013) outlines, the state refers to the physical condition of the environment resulting from pressures. Changes in the state impact the ecosystem balance, health levels, and the socio-economic conditions of the community.

Impact

The presence of macroplastic waste on beaches like Karangtawulan, Cipatujah, Sindangkerta, and Pamayangsari negatively affects coastal biodiversity and ecosystems. This pollution reduces the aesthetic value of the beaches, impacting tourism by decreasing visitor numbers. The litter poses threats to wildlife, such as hermit crabs and turtles, mistaking plastic for food or becoming entangled in it, which can lead to death.

Response

Addressing plastic waste is a multi-faceted issue requiring cross-sectoral collaboration. Local regulations in Tasikmalaya, such as PERDA no.3 of 2022 on waste management, and national policies like Perpres no.83 of 2018 on marine waste management, aim to tackle this issue. Educational initiatives and beach clean-up programs have been conducted but need to be more frequent to effectively reduce plastic waste along the Tasikmalaya coast.

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